

AN ANALYSIS OF VARIABLES INFLUENCING QUALITY OF TEACHERS IN SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

The paper reports the results of a study on the issues related to improving the quality factors of faculty members in Intermediate colleges in Uttar Pradesh. One of the primary indicators of quality of education is the quality of teaching faculty. Intermediate colleges in India constitute as one of the largest producer of technical manpower. A detailed survey has been conducted with the principals of the Intermediate colleges in Uttar Pradesh, India to understand the current issues in quality factors of faculty in Intermediate colleges. The pattern of the questionnaire instrument was devised in such a manner to obtain responses related to what does the principals look for in a prospective faculty candidate during interviews, factors affecting the recruitment process. The study also investigated the desirable profile of faculty members suitable for teaching job in Intermediate colleges. As an outcome of the study a conceptual framework was developed to provide guideline for grooming the new faculty and developing the experienced faculty. The study was conducted in the Intermediate colleges in Uttar Pradesh and the results are discussed.

Keywords: Quality factors, Recruitment, Training, Intermediate Colleges

1. INTRODUCTION

Education quality is a multi-dimensional concept and one of the indicators of quality is excellence of teachers (Shrivastava, 2003). The most important prerequisite for the development of technical education is the adequate supply of qualified teachers. Presently, the biggest challenge faced by technical educational institutions in India in general and Intermediate colleges in particular is the acute shortage of qualified and competent faculty members (Rao, 2006). Institutions are in a sheer dilemma on whether to improve the quality of existing faculty or to concentrate more on fresh recruitments. Another challenge faced by many institutions is the inconsistency in providing training to the faculty members. It is common to observe that the institutions spend much of their resources in recruiting suitable faculty members and retaining the existing faculty members. This clearly hampers other developmental activities which are very important. In the light of this prevailing condition, a study is necessary to understand the current issues faced by Intermediate colleges in developing the factors of teaching faculty and to evolve strategies to improve the quality of technical education in Intermediates.

2. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study is aimed to explore the perception of principals/vice principals of Intermediate colleges in Uttar Pradesh about the various aspects of quality attributes of faculty members in their institutions.

3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The study aimed to collect following aspects of information from the principals of Intermediates:

- What are the factors that principals expect from the prospective faculty candidate in the interview process?
- What are the common factors affecting the recruitment process to attract the competent faculty members into teaching profession in Intermediates?

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Design

The current study utilized descriptive research method to address the issues faced by Intermediate institutions in improving the quality of teaching faculty. Normally descriptive research is employed to portray the state of affairs as it exists at present (Kothari, 2004). Descriptive research often uses questionnaires and interviews to gather information from group of subjects (Ary et al., 2002). Current study utilized a survey questionnaire designed by the investigators to collect data from principals/vice principals regarding their perception about the quality of faculty members. The necessary input for developing the tool was obtained by seeking expert's opinion and reviewing the existing research literature. The study used closed choice (or multiple choice) questions which ask the respondent to choose, among a possible set of answers, the response that most closely represents his/her viewpoint (Kenneth, 2005).

3.2. Sample of the Study

The study employed convenience sampling which utilizes population elements selected for inclusion in the sample based on the ease of access (Kothari, 2004). The questionnaire was issued to 90 principals and vice principals of Intermediate colleges and the responses were received from 65 principals/vice principals. Thus the active sample size for the study was restricted to 65 principals/vice principals of Intermediate colleges in Uttar Pradesh, India.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Characteristics of Prospective Faculty Members

The first part of the questionnaire was intended to measure the important characteristics that principals look for or expect from a prospective faculty candidate during interview process. The graphical depiction of the results was as shown in **Figure 1**. The findings of the study are described below:

- Most of the principals (around 88% of the sample) agreed that the prospective faculty should have good communication skills. It is important to note that most of the principals favored in rating communication skills on a higher scale compared to technical skills.
- Around 59% of the respondents felt that technical skills are very important for the faculty members of Intermediate colleges.
- The survey indicated varied response to the query related to the academic record of the prospective faculty. Around 35% of administered sample of principals felt that academic record of the faculty candidate is very important. At the same time 41% of them felt that the academic record of the faculty candidate need not be a decisive factor in selecting the prospective faculty members during the recruitment process.
- Principals considered that the personality of the faculty candidates in terms of their and
- With respect to the question regarding the importance of additional qualifications of the faculty members, principals deemed that they were not the major factors in choices of selecting the faculty members during the interviews.

The above results clearly indicate that principals favor Communication skill as an important component for teaching in Intermediate colleges.

Figure 1: Characteristics of a Prospective Faculty

4.2. Factors Affecting Recruitment Process to Attract Competent Candidates

This section was intended to examine the opinion of principals regarding the factors influencing recruitment process to attract competent faculty candidates. The graphical depiction of the results was as shown in **Figure 2** and the findings are discussed below:

- Most of the principals (65% of the sample) stated that starting salary was always considered as the prime deciding factor in the recruitment process. Most of the candidates give more weightage to the starting salary.
- Principals also opined that facilities of the institute which includes infrastructure, transport and intellectual resouces play a significant role(59% of the sample) in attracting high caliber candidates.
- Principals felt that an institution with optimum workload comprising tecahing and non tecahing administrative workload can attract competent faculty candidate.
- The result reveals that promotion policy of the institute plays a decisive role in attracting bright candidate for the interview process.
- Nearly 30% of the administered sample of principals agreed that geographical location of the institution always affects the recruitment process while 23% agreed that geographical location of the institution need not be a decisive factor in recruitment process.

Figure 2: Factors Affecting Recruitment Process

5. FRAMEWORK FOR QUALITY IMPROVEMENT OF FACULTY MEMBERS IN POYTECHNIC COLLEGES

A conceptual framework has been developed based on the inputs given by the principals of Intermediates to impart training to the faculty members in Intermediate colleges. The salient features of the framework are described below.

5.1 Faculty Recruitment Process

Faculty recruitment process is the starting stage for the framework. A structured recruitment and selection process can be followed in the institutes. Once the recruitment process is completed, based on the work experience faculty members can be classified as new faculty and experienced faculty group.

5.2 Framework for New Faculty Development

It is recommended that the new faculty be taken through a systematic process to build their level of confidence and motivate them to stay focused in teaching profession for a longer tenure. Following are the stages involved in developing new and inexperienced faculty:

5.2.1 Mentoring Program

Mentoring is a relationship in which experienced faculty work with less experienced teachers to stimulate both academic and personal development (Luis et al., 2006). It becomes a way of revealing the secrets of the teaching profession or discipline for others, a process-oriented relationship involving knowledge acquisition, application, and critical reflection. The desirable role of a mentor to a new faculty member may be:

- Mentors should take the responsibility to help the new faculty to access the resources and facilities such as cabin and furniture, identity card, library card and other facilities as enjoyed by others.
- Mentors constantly provide input to the new faculty about the history and organizational structure of the institution, prevailing culture, rules and regulations as applicable to students and faculty.
- Mentors serve as experts in a subject matter or in instructional strategies often use various methods to foster the skills of mentees.
- Mentors should constantly motivate and encourage the new faculty members in their initial days.

Thus the whole concept of mentoring revolves around developing a rapport between the new faculty and the institution, to enable them to stay motivated and committed to the profession.

5.2.2. New Faculty Induction/Training Program

It is recommended that the new faculty members shall undergo Faculty Development Program (FDP) conducted by government organizations such as National Institute of Technical Teachers Training and Research (NITTTR), Chennai, Department of Technical Education (DTE), All India Council of Technical Education (AICTE) in the initial days of their career to build their confidence in teaching and to develop leadership skills, communication and teamwork skills.

Figure 5: Framework for quality improvement of new faculty in Intermediates

5.3. Framework for Quality Improvement of Experienced Faculty Members

The experienced faculty in Intermediates comes from various sources such as from other Intermediates, nearby industries and candidate from other industry/service sector who wish to migrate to teaching for various reasons. Hence training is required but not to the extent as required for inexperienced faculty members. The sequences of stages required for developing experienced faculty are listed below.

5.3.1. Faculty Induction

Induction program for faculty members is often overlooked in the educational institutions when compared to the industry. Faculty Induction program shall be organized by head of the department. The induction program serves the following purposes

- To introduce the new faculty members to the teaching and non teaching members of the department.

- To highlight the achievements, accomplishments, areas of expertise and experience of the new faculty members to the department people.
- To create an impression among the faculty members to feel how important they are to the department and institute.

5.3.2. Need Analysis

The framework also suggests that the Need Analysis may be performed by head of the department or senior faculty for the experienced faculty to analyze the potential skills already possessed by him and identifies the skills areas which needed improvement. Depending on the input from the need analysis, the faculty members may be recommended to undergo training program or can act as a team player and resource person in organizing various technical and cultural events.

5.4. Periodic Assessment and Feedback

Assessment and feedback should be considered as a continuous process and should not be seen as an end semester/year activity. The assessment process shall be carried out with genuine purpose to improve the skills of faculty members in their lecturing, problem solving, student interaction and classroom management.

6. FRAMEWORK FOR SKILL DEVELOPMENT OF FACULTY MEMBERS IN INTERMEDIATES

A conceptual framework has been evolved to provide guidelines for skill development of faculty members in Intermediate colleges. The salient features of the framework are described below.

6.1. Framework

A framework has been evolved to provide guidelines for developing skillset of existing/experienced faculty members of Intermediate colleges. The various stages involved in the framework are described below.

6.2. Existing Faculty - Skill Analysis

The existing faculty is taken through a “Skill Analysis” process with the following objectives:

- Identify the most prominent skills visible among the faculty members in areas such as technical, professional, leadership, management capabilities, communication and soft skills.
- Identify the existence of basic skills necessary for the individual faculty members to sustain and grow in the teaching profession.
- Identify the competent faculty members with skill sets that can be disseminated to other members of the faculty community.

6.3. Classification and Forming of Identical Skill Groups

This activity of Classification and Forming of identical skill groups can be performed in each department so that skill set groups can be formed within a department. For example faculty

members with keen research interest and experience in Manufacturing Technology can be identified and grouped under Manufacturing Technology Group and so on. Similarly many such groups can be formed in each department.

Figure 6: A conceptual framework for Skill development of Faculty in Intermediates

6.4. Identification of Lacking Skill Groups

An important task of the Head of the department is to identify the skill groups which are very much lacking in their department. Care should be taken in this process that they cannot afford to list too many lacking skill groups, since acquiring the lacking skills may become complicated process. Hence depending on the context, resource and market demand, decision should be arrived among the heads of the departments and institutional head to list the lacking skill groups.

6.5. Formation of Search Committee

After a consensus is reached between the heads of the departments and institutional head , it is vital to provide guidelines to the search committees and focus groups to recruit faculty from the lacking skill groups.

6.6. Knowledge Sharing across the Groups

Once skill groups are identified within the department, the head of the department can organize knowledge sharing sessions within the department or in collaboration with other departments if necessary as is the case with interdisciplinary areas and facilitate dissemination of skills across groups. The ideas behind the Sharing of Knowledge/Skills are

- To promote confidence among the groups to exhibit their competency in the acquired and nurtured skills.
- By sharing the skills the teachers can realize how far they are advanced or what kind of improvement they require in communication and presentation aspects.
- To create awareness among new/inexperienced faculty of the availability of various skill groups and to align them among the skill groups which is of particular interest to the.
- To promote continuous learning among the teaching faculty by belonging to the available skill group, teamwork and group learning.
- To constantly motivate young and experienced faculty members to improve their skills by demonstrating and availing feedback from the learning community.
- To create a competitive and vibrant atmosphere among the faculty members to learn, exhibit their knowledge and to earn appreciation and applauses.

7. CONCLUSIONS

It was observed from the study that principals of the Intermediate colleges are very keen in recruiting and retaining competent faculty. Hence the following statements are reiterated to stress the importance of quality of faculty in teaching

- New initiatives are necessary from the administrators of Intermediate colleges to inculcate good communication and presentation skills to the faculty members through proper training.
- Moreover search committees and recruitment panel can give more importance to select candidates with good communication and presentation skills during recruitment process.
- Administrators has to believe that quality of the teaching faculty and learning of the students can be enhanced by inducting their faculty members for various interventions programs such as Faculty Development Programs(FDP), Finishing School Training Programs and other Training Programs conducted by NITTTRs, DTE, AICTE and other bodies.
- Institutions may develop suitable system and process to establish intellectual knowledge base which can serve as body of knowledge to promote technical competence among teaching fraternity.
- It should be recognized that salary plays a significant role in attracting bright candidates to the teaching profession in Intermediates.

The study has successfully identified key factors to promote, aspects to change in developing the faculty members of Intermediates. The framework thus developed as an outcome of this study can become useful to the society if it is implemented in their institutes.

8. REFERENCES

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